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AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
HEALTH INSURANCE CLAIM MANAGEMENT
SYSTEM PROJECT
BY
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Date: 2023/08/27

HEALTH INSURANCE CLAIM MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

ABSTRACT:

This project is designed by considering importance of developing software application for handling insurance details of customers which are presently maintained manually in the form of records. This project helps the user to maintain the database of any insurance company and also can update the details of the insurance with the details of the patients along with the hospital side information. The main aim of developing this Insurance Management System is to provide efficient management service to the customer and insurance offices and as well as hospitals. This insurance management system is fully customized desktop application where company can view each patient detail and maintain them efficiently It provides a user-friendly web pages and effective medium to the patients and to the insurance company. This system used to the consumer for reduces their time to waiting for getting insurance and it used to the insurance agency for reduce the work for verify the details which is given by the patients.

OBJECTIVE

The main intention of introducing this system is to secure the patient file using Blockchain technique identifying patient and company information using identifying mechanism, insurance provider using this website for providing better customer services ,Insurance Companies use it keep tracking customer, owner details and physical verification of the customer etc.

ALGORITHM

MODULES:

- Register
- Login
- View Insurance Information
- View Patient Information
- Apply Emergency Insurance
- Apply Planned Insurance
- View Approved Insurance
- Insurance Status

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

Hardware Requirements:

- Processor : Intel processor 3.0 GHz
- RAM : 2GB
- Hard disk : 500 GB
- Compact Disk : 650 Mb
- Keyboard : Standard keyboard
- Mouse : Logitech mouse
- Monitor : 15 inch color monitor

Software Requirements:

- Front End : PHP
- Back End : MYSQL
- Server : WAMP
- Operating System : Windows OS
- System type : 32-bit or 64-bit Operating System
- IDE : DREAMWEAVER
- DLL : Depends upon the title

SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

PHP - Overview

PHP is a recursive acronym for "PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor". PHP is a server side scripting language that is embedded in HTML. It is used to manage dynamic content, databases, session tracking, even build entire e-commerce sites. The PHP Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP) is a programming language that allows web developers to create dynamic content that interacts with databases. PHP is basically used for developing web based software applications. This tutorial helps you to build your base with PHP.

Why to Learn PHP?

PHP started out as a small open source project that evolved as more and more people found out how useful it was. Rasmus Lerdorf unleashed the first version of PHP way back in 1994.

PHP is a MUST for students and working professionals to become a great Software Engineer specially when they are working in Web Development Domain. I will list down some of the key advantages of learning PHP:

- PHP is a recursive acronym for "PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor".
- PHP is a server side scripting language that is embedded in HTML. It is used to manage dynamic content, databases, session tracking, even build entire e-commerce sites.
- It is integrated with a number of popular databases, including MySQL, PostgreSQL, Oracle, Sybase, Informix, and Microsoft SQL Server.
- PHP is pleasingly zippy in its execution, especially when compiled as an Apache module on the Unix side. The MySQL server, once started, executes even very complex queries with huge result sets in record-setting time.

- PHP supports a large number of major protocols such as POP3, IMAP, and LDAP. PHP4 added support for Java and distributed object architectures (COM and CORBA), making n-tier development a possibility for the first time.
- PHP is forgiving: PHP language tries to be as forgiving as possible.
- PHP Syntax is C-Like.

Fig 1: Basic View of PHP

Characteristics of PHP

Five important characteristics make PHP's practical nature possible –

- Simplicity
- Efficiency
- Security
- Flexibility
- Familiarity

Hello World using PHP.

Just to give you a little excitement about PHP, I'm going to give you a small conventional PHP Hello World program, You can try it using Demo link.

```
<html>
  <head>
    <title>Hello World</title>
  </head>
```

```
<body>
  <?php echo "Hello, World!";?>
</body> </html>
```

Applications of PHP

As mentioned before, PHP is one of the most widely used language over the web. I'm going to list few of them here:

PHP performs system functions, i.e. from files on a system it can create, open, read, write, and close them. and can handle forms, i.e. gather data from files, save data to a file, through email you can send data, return data to the user. You add, delete, modify elements within your database through PHP and access cookies variables and set cookies. Using PHP, you can restrict users to access some pages of your website and encrypt data.

Architecture Overview

This section explains how all the different parts of the driver fit together. From the different language runtimes, through the extension and to the PHP libraries on top. This new architecture has replaced the old mongo extension. We refer to the new one as the *mongodb* extension.

Fig 2: Overview of PHP

At the top of this stack sits a pure [» PHP library](#), which we will distribute as a Composer package. This library will provide an API similar to what users have come to expect from the old mongo driver (e.g. CRUD methods, database and collection objects, command helpers) and we expect it to be a common dependency for most applications built with MongoDB. This library will also implement common [» specifications](#), in the interest of improving API consistency across all of the [» drivers](#) maintained by MongoDB (and hopefully some community drivers, too). Sitting below that library we have the lower level driver. This extension will effectively form the glue between PHP and our system libraries. This extension will expose an identical public API for the most essential and performance-sensitive functionality:

- Connection management
- BSON encoding and decoding
- Object document serialization (to support ODM libraries)
- Executing commands and write operations
- Handling queries and cursors

Prerequisites

Before proceeding with this tutorial you should have at least basic understanding of computer programming, Internet, Database, and MySQL etc is very helpful.

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Common uses of PHP

- PHP performs system functions, i.e. from files on a system it can create, open, read, write, and close them.
- PHP can handle forms, i.e. gather data from files, save data to a file, through email you can send data, return data to the user.
- You add, delete, modify elements within your database through PHP. Access cookies variables and set cookies. Using PHP, you can restrict users to access some pages of your website. It can encrypt data.

Characteristics of PHP

Five important characteristics make PHP's practical nature possible –

- Simplicity
- Efficiency
- Security
- Flexibility
- Familiarity

In order to develop and run PHP Web pages three vital components need to be installed on your computer system.

- **Web Server** – PHP will work with virtually all Web Server software, including Microsoft's Internet Information Server (IIS) but then most often used is freely available Apache Server. Download Apache for free here – <https://httpd.apache.org/download.cgi>
- **Database** – PHP will work with virtually all database software, including Oracle and Sybase but most commonly used is freely available MySQL database. Download MySQL for free here – <https://www.mysql.com/downloads/>
- **PHP Parser** – In order to process PHP script instructions a parser must be installed to generate HTML output that can be sent to the Web Browser. This tutorial will guide you how to install PHP parser on your computer.

PHP Parser Installation

Before you proceed it is important to make sure that you have proper environment setup on your machine to develop your web programs using PHP.

Type the following address into your browser's address box.

<http://127.0.0.1/info.php>

If this displays a page showing your PHP installation related information then it means you have PHP and Webserver installed properly. Otherwise you have to follow given procedure to install PHP on your computer.

This section will guide you to install and configure PHP over the following four platforms –

- [PHP Installation on Linux or Unix with Apache](#)
- [PHP Installation on Mac OS X with Apache](#)
- [PHP Installation on Windows NT/2000/XP with IIS](#)
- [PHP Installation on Windows NT/2000/XP with Apache](#)

Apache Configuration

If you are using Apache as a Web Server then this section will guide you to edit Apache Configuration Files.

Just Check it here – [PHP Configuration in Apache Server](#)

PHP.INI File Configuration

The PHP configuration file, php.ini, is the final and most immediate way to affect PHP's functionality.

Just Check it here – [PHP.INI File Configuration](#)

Windows IIS Configuration

To configure IIS on your Windows machine you can refer your IIS Reference Manual shipped along with IIS.

The main way to store information in the middle of a PHP program is by using a variable.

Here are the most important things to know about variables in PHP.

- All variables in PHP are denoted with a leading dollar sign (\$).
- The value of a variable is the value of its most recent assignment.
- Variables are assigned with the = operator, with the variable on the left-hand side and the expression to be evaluated on the right.
- Variables can, but do not need, to be declared before assignment.
- Variables in PHP do not have intrinsic types - a variable does not know in advance whether it will be used to store a number or a string of characters.
- Variables used before they are assigned have default values.
- PHP does a good job of automatically converting types from one to another when necessary.
- PHP variables are Perl-like.

PHP has a total of eight data types which we use to construct our variables –

- **Integers** – are whole numbers, without a decimal point, like 4195.
- **Doubles** – are floating-point numbers, like 3.14159 or 49.1.
- **Booleans** – have only two possible values either true or false.
- **NULL** – is a special type that only has one value: NULL.
- **Strings** – are sequences of characters, like 'PHP supports string operations.'
- **Arrays** – are named and indexed collections of other values.
- **Objects** – are instances of programmer-defined classes, which can package up both other kinds of values and functions that are specific to the class.
- **Resources** – are special variables that hold references to resources external to PHP (such as database connections).

Conclusion

FINAL THOUGHT: it's very important to learn an entire subject matter. As a programmer-in-the-making, you may be inclined to take what you've learned and start coding immediately, but before you've learned enough of the topic at large. In reality this will lead to

you coding away, and then eventually spending hours just to research how to solve one little aspect you need. If you learned the whole subject matter of, say, procedural PHP, you most likely will have naturally encountered that solution, and in a fraction of the time! Often it can take very many hours to research one small solution that results in one line of code.

Fig3 : Evolution of Various Scripts

Whereas learning that trick might have been a natural thing to learn as part of learning the whole subject, and only requires 5 minutes of study in between learning many other tricks. In other words, a developer that has to constantly seek out solutions to things he/she doesn't know will waste a lot more time in aggregate than someone that mastered the subject as a whole, and then went to apply it. You're just more relaxed and in a better learning mode when you're focused on nothing but learning. But when you're focused on producing results, and have to learn at the same time, it can be stressful and waste you tons of time going back and forth from testing each of the tens of wrong solutions you're trying out and googling until you find the right one.

MYSQL

MySQL is the most popular Open Source Relational SQL Database Management System. MySQL is one of the best RDBMS being used for developing various web-based software applications. MySQL is developed, marketed and supported by MySQL AB, which is a Swedish company. This tutorial will give you a quick start to MySQL and make you comfortable with MySQL programming.

Fig 4: Structure of Data Directory

MySQL Database

MySQL is a fast, easy-to-use RDBMS being used for many small and big businesses. MySQL is developed, marketed and supported by MySQL AB, which is a Swedish company. MySQL is becoming so popular because of many good reasons –

- MySQL is released under an open-source license. So you have nothing to pay to use it.
- MySQL is a very powerful program in its own right. It handles a large subset of the functionality of the most expensive and powerful database packages.
- MySQL uses a standard form of the well-known SQL data language.
- MySQL works on many operating systems and with many languages including PHP, PERL, C, C++, JAVA, etc.
- MySQL works very quickly and works well even with large data sets.
- MySQL is very friendly to PHP, the most appreciated language for web development.

- MySQL supports large databases, up to 50 million rows or more in a table. The default file size limit for a table is 4GB, but you can increase this (if your operating system can handle it) to a theoretical limit of 8 million terabytes (TB).
- MySQL is customizable. The open-source GPL license allows programmers to modify the MySQL software to fit their own specific environments.

MYSQL Functions

Here is the list of all important MySQL functions. Each function has been explained along with suitable example.

- MySQL Group By Clause – The MySQL GROUP BY statement is used along with the SQL aggregate functions like SUM to provide means of grouping the result dataset by certain database table column(s).
- MySQL COUNT Function – The MySQL COUNT aggregate function is used to count the number of rows in a database table.
- MySQL MAX Function – The MySQL MAX aggregate function allows us to select the highest (maximum) value for a certain column.
- MySQL MIN Function – The MySQL MIN aggregate function allows us to select the lowest (minimum) value for a certain column.
- MySQL SUM Function – The MySQL SUM aggregate function allows selecting the total for a numeric column.
- MySQL CONCAT Function – This is used to concatenate any string inside any MySQL command.
- MySQL DATE and Time Functions – Complete list of MySQL Date and Time related functions.
- MySQL Numeric Functions – Complete list of MySQL functions required to manipulate numbers in MySQL.
- MySQL String Functions – Complete list of MySQL functions required to manipulate strings in MySQL.

Discussion

MySQL is the most popular Open Source Relational SQL Database Management System. MySQL is one of the best RDBMS being used for developing various web-based software applications. MySQL is developed, marketed and supported by MySQL AB, which is a Swedish company. This tutorial will give you a quick start to MySQL and make you comfortable with MySQL programming.

WAMP Server

WAMP is an acronym that stands for Windows, Apache, MySQL, and PHP. It's a software stack which means installing WAMP installs Apache, MySQL, and PHP on your operating system (Windows in the case of WAMP). Even though you can install them separately, they are usually bundled up, and for a good reason too.

What's good to know is that WAMP derives from LAMP (the L stands for Linux). The only difference between these two is that WAMP is used for Windows, while LAMP – for Linux based operating systems.

Let's quickly go over what each letter represents “**W**” stands for Windows, there's also LAMP (for Linux) and MAMP (for Mac). “**A**” stands for Apache. Apache is the server software that is responsible for serving web pages. When you request a page to be seen by you, Apache grants your request over HTTP and shows you the site. “**M**” stands for MySQL. MySQL's job is to be the database management system for your server. It stores all of the relevant information like your site's content, user profiles, etc. “**P**” stands for PHP. It's the programming language that was used to write WordPress. It acts like glue for this whole software stack. PHP is running in conjunction with Apache and communicating with MySQL.

Fig 6: WAMP Structure

Instead of installing and testing WordPress on your hosting account, you can do it on your personal computer (localhost).

WAMP acts like a virtual server on your computer. It allows you to test all WordPress features without any consequences since it's localized on your machine and is not connected to the web.

First of all, this means that you don't need to wait until files are uploaded to your site, and secondly – this makes creating backups much easier.

WAMP speeds up the work process for both developers and theme designers alike. What is more, you also get the benefit of playing around with your site to your heart's content. However, to actually make the website go live, you need to get some form of hosting service and a Domain. See our beginner-friendly article about web hosting for more information. In essence, WAMP is used as a safe space to work on your website, without needing to actually host it online. WAMP also has a control panel. Once you install the software package, all of the services mentioned above (excluding the operating system that is) will be installed on your local machine. Whether you use WAMP or software packages for the other operating systems, it's a great way to save time. You won't have to upload files to a site and will be able to learn how to develop in a safe and care-free environment.

References

- Acharya, Kamal. "STUDENT INFORMATION MANAGEMENT SYSTEM." *Authorea Preprints* (2023).
- Acharya, Kamal. "Library Management System." Available at SSRN4807104 (2019).
- ACHARYA, KAMAL, et al. "LIBRARY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM." (2019).
- Acharya, Kamal. "Online bus reservation system project report." *Authorea Preprints* (2024).
- Acharya, Kamal. "Online bus reservation system project report." (2024).
- Acharya, Kamal. "Online Bus Reservation System." *SSRN ElectroNIC ASIA Journal* (2024): n. pag.
- Acharya, Kamal. "Student Information Management System Project." *SSRN ElectroNIC ASIA Journal* (2024): n. pag.
- Acharya, Kamal. "ATTENDANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM." *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science* (2023): n. pag.
- Acharya, Kamal. "College Information Management System." *SSRN ElectroNIC ASIA Journal* (2024): n. pag.
- Acharya, Kamal, *Attendance Management System Project* (April 28, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4810251> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4810251>
- Acharya, Kamal, *Online Food Order System* (May 2, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814732> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814732>
- Acharya, Kamal, *University management system project*. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814103> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814103>
- Acharya, Kamal, *Online banking management system*. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4813597> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4813597>
- Acharya, Kamal, *Online Job Portal Management System* (May 5, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4817534> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4817534>
- Acharya, Kamal, *Employee leave management system*. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819626> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819626>
- Acharya, Kamal, *Online electricity billing project report*. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819630> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819630>
- Acharya, Kamal, *POLICY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831694> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831694>
- Acharya, Kamal, *Online job placement system project report*. (January 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831638> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831638>
- Acharya, Kamal, *Software testing for project report*. (May 16, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831028> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831028>
- Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE CRIME REPORTING SYSTEM PROJECT*. (August 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831015> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831015>
- Acharya, Kamal, *Burger ordering system project report*. (October 10, 2022). Available at

SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4832704> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4832704>

Acharya, Kamal, Teachers Record Management System Project Report (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4833821> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4833821>

Acharya, Kamal, Dairy Management System Project Report (December 20, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835231> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835231>

Acharya, Kamal, Electrical Shop Management System Project (December 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835238> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835238>

Acharya, Kamal, Online book store management system project report. (February 10, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835277> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835277>

Acharya, Kamal, Paint shop management system project report. (January 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835441> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835441>

Acharya, Kamal, Supermarket billing system project report. (August 10, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835474> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835474>

Acharya, Kamal, Online taxi booking system project report. (March 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837729> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837729>

Acharya, Kamal, Online car servicing system project report. (March 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837832> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837832>

Acharya, Kamal, School management system project report. (July 10, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837837> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837837>

Acharya, Kamal, Furniture Showroom Management System Project Report (March 21, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839422> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839422>

Acharya, Kamal, Online Vehicle Rental System Project Report (March 21, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839429> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839429>

Acharya, Kamal, Fruit Shop Management System Project Report (August 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841048> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841048>

Acharya, Kamal, Hall Booking Management System Project Report (December 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841055> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841055>

Acharya, Kamal, Laundry Management System Project Report (October 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841059> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841059>

Acharya, Kamal, A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT (September 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841209> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841209>

Acharya, Kamal, A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT (May 25, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841210> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841210>

Acharya, Kamal, ONLINE DATING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842066> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842066>

Acharya, Kamal, ONLINE RESUME BUILDER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842071> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842071>

Acharya, Kamal, TOLL TEX MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT (August 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842082> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842082>

Acharya, Kamal, Chat Application Through Client Server Management System Project Report (June 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842761> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842761>

Acharya, Kamal, Web Chatting Application Management System Project Report (April 25, 2022).

Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842771> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842771>

Acharya, Kamal, Automobile management system project report (May 25, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846917> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846917>

Acharya, Kamal, College bus management system project report (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846920> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846920>

Acharya, Kamal, Courier management system project report (May 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846922> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846922>

Acharya, Kamal, Event management system project report (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846927> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846927>

Acharya, Kamal, Library management system project report II (May 25, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4848857> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4848857>